

PRECIPITATION CHARACTERISTICS OF SiC WHISKER REINFORCED Al-Cu AND Al-Cu-Mg ALLOYS

H.I. Lee and K.H. Oh

(Materials Eng. Div., Korea Advanced Institute of Science and
Technology, Seoul, Korea)

T.S. Kim and T.H. Kim

(Dept. of Metallurgical Eng., Seoul National University, Seoul, Korea)

ABSTRACT

Studies carried out to investigate the effects of SiC whisker reinforcement on the precipitation characteristics of Al-Cu and Al-Cu-Mg alloy. The materials in this study were processed by a powder metallurgy technique and squeeze casting. Precipitation characteristics of the processed materials were investigated using macrohardness measurement, differential scanning calorimetry, and transmission electron microscopy after various thermal treatments. The results of macrohardness measurements indicated that the age-hardening in SiC whisker reinforced Al-Cu alloy was retarded. Calorimetric measurements and transmission electron micrographs revealed that the suppression of θ'' formation by introducing SiC whisker reinforcement plays an important role in those phenomena. The aging sequence of the Al-Cu-Mg alloy was altered by the introduction of the SiC whiskers. Precipitation of θ'' and θ' by solute depletion was considered to be the reason for it. Transmission electron micrographs for the SiC whisker reinforced material showed the PFZ formation in the vicinity of the interface between matrix and large whiskers.

INTRODUCTION

Recently some works^{1,2,3,4,5} were reported on the precipitation behavior of the ceramic reinforced aluminum metal-matrix composites. Accelerated aging phenomenon have been reported in the 6061 Al-23vol.%B₄C_p composite¹ and in the 2124 Al-15wt%SiC_w composite². In such a phenomenon it was suggested² that a high density of dislocation due to differential thermal contraction between matrix and reinforcement plays an important role. The suppression of GP zone formation have also been reported in the 6061 Al and Al-4wt%Cu sintered with Al₂O₃^{3,4} and in the 6061 Al- δ alumina fibre composite⁵. Those phenomena was attributed to the absence of quenched in vacancies. However, the precipitation characteristics of aluminum metal-matrix could be affected by other effects. For example, Nutt and Carpenter⁶ reported the interfacial segregation of Mg and the heterogeneous distribution of matrix phases in the 15 vol.% SiC whisker reinforced 2124 aluminum alloy.

In subsequent studies^{7,8} on the SiC whisker reinforced 7xxx and 2xxx aluminum alloys authors in this work found that the control of matrix properties is very important to enhance the properties of composites. In this study we investigated the precipitation characteristics of SiC whisker reinforced Al-4wt%Cu alloys processed by P/M techniques and Al 2024 processed by P/M technique and squeeze casting. For comparison purposes monolithic Al-4w.%Cu alloy and Al 2024 were processed by the same technique. The age hardening behavior of the processed material were studied using

macrohardness measurement, differential scanning calorimetry, and transmission electron microscopy. The results in this work allowed us to compare the precipitation behavior of the SiC whisker reinforced and unreinforced aluminum alloys.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Al-4wt%Cu powders were prepared from pure aluminum and copper of purity 99.9% by inert gas atomization. Aluminum alloy 2024 powders (of nominal composition Al-4.5wt%Cu-1.5wt%Mg) were purchased from Korea Nonferrous Metal Powder Co(KMNPC). Prepared powders were mechanically sieved to -230mesh ($< 63\mu\text{m}$). The β -type SiC whiskers were purchased from Tateho Chemical Co in Japan. The average dimensions of the whiskers were $0.5\mu\text{m}$ in diameter and $50\mu\text{m}$ in length before processing. Gas atomized Al-4wt% powders were mixed with 5,10,15 wt% SiC whisker dispersed using supersonic stirrer in buthanol. After 3 hours mixing in a rotating mill, the powders blended with SiC whisker were filtered using aspirator and dried for 10 hours at 463K in the oven. The powders were then hot pressed using the pressure 75kgf/cm^2 for 15min at 863K and unreinforced material was processed from the same powder batch. Aluminum alloy 2024, reinforced with 17wt% SiC whisker was processed by P/M technique. For comparison purposes, aluminum alloy 2024, reinforced with 27wt% SiC whisker and unreinforced, were squeeze casted using the pressure 50MPa at 800K.

The whisker reinforced and unreinforced materials were cutted in the form of small block and had identical thermal processing history. Al-4wt%Cu alloy and its composites were solutionized for 2 hours at 793K, quenched in ice water and then artificially aged in silicon oil bath at 433K and 468K for various times. Aluminum alloy 2024 and its composites were solutionized at 763K for 2 hours, water quenched and then artificially aged at 443K for various times. Because of the possibility of room temperature aging all of the specimens were stored in a freezer after solution treatment and artificial aging.

Vickers hardness measurements on heat treated specimens were made using a diamond piramid indenter and a 5kgf load. At least 6 hardness measurements were made for each aging condition to ensure accurate results. Specimens for DSC analysis were prepared in the form of disk 5mm in diameter, 0.4mm in thickness and were investigated using heat compensation type ULVAC DSC 7000 with a plug-in DSC cell. All of the DSC runs starting at room temperature, ended at 803K and were made for a constant heating rate of 5K/min. The alumina of approximately equal mass was used as a reference material. The specific heat versus temperature curve was normalized for the unit mass of metal-matrix. TEM specimens were prepared from 0.4mm thick plate cutted using a jewellers saw and were mechanically polished to a thickness of about $40\mu\text{m}$. Final thinning were carried out using ion mill, operating at 4kV, ion current of 5-15mA and a sample inclination of 15° to the ion beam. The unreinforced materials were thinned in a twin jet polisher with a 10% perchloric acid, 90% methanol using a potential of 25V at a temperature of about -25°C . Some of the SiC whisker reinforced materials were also prepared by the same techniques. The thin foils were examined in a detail using JEOL 200CX transmission electron microscopy operating at 160kV.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig.1 shows the variation of macrohardness as a function of aging times for the whisker reinforced and unreinforced Al-4wt%Cu aged at 433K. As expected, it can be found that the hardness of materials, solution treated and water quenched, increases evenly with the increase of reinforced SiC whisker content. However, there are noticeable differences in age hardening behavior between the reinforced and unreinforced materials. Whereas the peak aging time is about 12 hours in the unreinforced material, the whisker reinforced materials exhibit maximum hardness after 1-2 days of aging. Another interesting feature of this figure is the noticeable difference in the magnitude of age hardening. The amount of age hardening is about 30Hv in the whisker reinforced materials, which

is smaller than that in the unreinforced material by the 20Hv. The variation of the peak aging time as a function of reinforced SiC whisker content is not discernable in the figures.

Fig.1 The result of vickers hardness measurement for the materials aged at 433K.

Fig.2 The result of DSC measurement for the materials, solution treated for 2 hours at 793K and quenched in water.

- (a) Al-4wt%Cu
- (b) Al-4wt%Cu, reinforced with 5wt% SiC whiskers
- (c) Al-4wt%Cu, reinforced with 10wt% SiC whiskers
- (d) Al-4wt%Cu, reinforced with 15wt% SiC whiskers

Fig.2 shows the results of the calorimetric measurements as a function of SiC whisker content after solution treatment and water quenching. In the unreinforced material by P/M techniques, the precipitation and dissolution of the various metastable phases (GP zones, θ'' , θ' and θ) occurred at lower temperature than those in a single crystalline material⁹. The endothermic reaction starting at 360K is due to the reversion of GP zones, which means the formation of GP zone below 360K. The two exothermic reactions, which exhibit peak at 458K and 523K, are due to the precipitation of metastable phases (primarily θ'' and θ'). The endothermic reactions above 600K are due to the dissolution of θ'' , θ' and the growth of precipitates θ . When the material is reinforced with SiC whiskers, it is noticeable that the first exothermic peak decreases as the reinforced SiC whisker content increases. However, a difference in the peak temperature on the DSC curves is not discernable.

Fig.3 TEM micrographs for the Al-4wt%Cu, solution treated and artificially aged.
 (a) after 5 hours aging at 433K
 (b) after 5 hours aging at 468K

Microstructural development of the unreinforced material during the artificial aging are demonstrated in Fig.3. The densely precipitated θ'' in the matrix and the inhomogeneously precipitated θ on grain boundary are shown in TEM micrographs of the unreinforced material aged for 5 hours at 433K (Fig.3(a)). Although inhomogeneously nucleated θ' on dislocations and θ on grain boundary were found in the matrix, the magnitude was very small. The microstructure of the unreinforced material aged for 5 hours at 468K is consisted of the precipitates θ' in the matrix and θ on grain boundary (Fig.3(b)). The precipitate θ'' was not discernable in this magnification.

Fig.4 TEM micrographs for the 15wt% SiC whisker reinforced Al-4wt%Cu, solution treated and artificially aged at 433K for 5 hours.

The microstructure of the 15 wt% SiC whisker reinforced material aged for 5 hours at 433K is shown in Fig.4. These figures show the microstructure consisted of the precipitate θ' in the matrix and θ on grain boundary. An important feature of this figure is that there does not appear to be θ'' in the matrix (Fig.4(a) and (b)). Although no preferential nucleation of the precipitates near the interface between the whisker and matrix is found, there are some evidence of inhomogenous nucleation of θ' (probably on dislocations) in the whisker-rich regions (Fig.4(b)).

Fig.5 The result of DSC measurement for the materials, solution treated for 2 hours at 763K and quenched in water.

- (a) 2024 Al alloy, processed by squeeze casting
- (b) 17wt% SiC whisker reinforced 2024 Al alloy, processed by P/M technic
- (c) 27wt% SiC whisker reinforced 2024 Al alloy, processed by squeeze casting

Fig.5 shows the results of calorimetric measurements for the unreinforced and reinforced aluminum alloy 2024, solutionized and water quenched. The endothermic reaction starting at about 450K is due to the reversion of GPB zones. The exothermic reaction which exhibits peak at 523K is mainly due to the precipitation of S' . The endothermic reaction starting at about 630K is due to the dissolution of precipitate S' . When aluminum alloy 2024 was reinforced with SiC whiskers, the precipitation behavior was altered as shown in Fig.5(b) and (c). New exothermic reaction between 450K and 500K is observed. It is the same phenomenon reported by other researcher¹⁰. The new exothermic reaction in the 27wt% SiC whisker reinforced Al 2024 occurs at more higher temperature than that in the 17wt% SiC whisker reinforced Al 2024 by P/M. The intensity of the new exothermic reaction is also increasing as the content of SiC whisker reinforcements increases.

The microstructure of whisker reinforced aluminum alloy 2024 aged for 8 hours at 463K is shown in Fig.6. There exists precipitate-free-zone (PFZ) on grain boundary(Fig.6(a)). It is noticeable that PFZ also exist near the interface between whisker and aluminum matrix(Fig.6(b), (c)). The precipitates shown in Fig.6 were S' and θ' which are shown as fine needles or lathes.

Fig.6 TEM micrographs for the 27wt% SiC whisker reinforced 2024 Al alloy, solution treated for 2 hours at 763K and artificially aged for 8 hours at 463K.

- (a) PFZ near the grain boundary
- (b) PFZ near SiC whiskers
- (c) PFZ between SiC whiskers

DISCUSSION

1. Retarded age-hardening behavior in the SiC whisker reinforced Al-4wt%Cu alloy

The present work clearly indicates that the peak aging time in the whisker reinforced Al-Cu metal-matrix composite is significantly retarded as shown in Fig.1. Another interesting feature is that the magnitude of hardening by artificial aging is much smaller in the whisker reinforced material than that in the unreinforced material. The reason for these could be explained from the differences in DSC curves and TEM micrographs for the reinforced and unreinforced materials. The DSC measurements for solution treated and quenched materials shows that the first exothermic reaction at about 458K gradually disappears as the content of reinforced whisker increases (Fig.2). TEM micrographs for the SiC whisker reinforced and unreinforced materials aged for 5 hours at 433K show the different microstructure. Whereas θ'' is precipitated densely in the matrix of the unreinforced material, it is not discernable in the matrix of the whisker reinforced material (Fig.3 and 4). Through these observations we could conclude that the first exothermic reaction shown in the DSC curve of the unreinforced material is due to the precipitation of θ'' and its formation is suppressed by the introduction of SiC whiskers.

The suppression of θ'' precipitation has been reported in the prestrained Al-Cu matrix^{11,12}. Although the reason for this is not yet clear, it was suggested by Graf and Guinier¹¹ that θ'' could only nucleate on $\{100\}_{Al}$ planes and these are so distorted in the prestrained material that nucleation could not take place. In SiC whisker reinforced materials, such a high strain could be generated by the differential thermal contraction between the matrix and reinforcement. Rough estimate indicates that the strain between Al metal-matrix and SiC whisker introduced by water quenching from 793K is about 1%. Numerical analysis¹³ using finite element method indicated that the stress concentration at the matrix-whisker interface is sufficient to yield matrix. In an *in situ* high voltage electron microscopy study on the Al-SiC whisker composite, Vogelsang *et al.*¹⁴ have reported such a dislocation generation during cooling. These experimental evidence and analysis strongly

suggest that the suppression of θ'' formation is done by a high density of dislocation and a strain generated during cooling.

2. Precipitation behavior of the SiC whisker reinforced 2024 Al alloy

The results of the calorimetric measurement for the SiC whisker reinforced 2024 Al alloy showed that the new exothermic reaction occurred between 450-500K. Kamio¹⁶ reported the similar phenomenon in the SiC whisker reinforced Al-4wt%Cu-0.5wt%Mg alloy. It was suggested that such a phenomenon was due to the precipitation of θ' . But compared with the results of the SiC whisker reinforced Al-4wt%Cu, we concluded that that reaction was due to the precipitation of θ'' by solute depletion at the matrix-whisker interface. The precipitation of θ' at about 523K was probably overlapped to the precipitation of S' at the same temperature. The broadening of the exothermic reaction at about 523K in the SiC whisker reinforced material (Fig.5) and TEM micrographs for the material aged at 443K (Fig.6) support such a suggestion. Solute depletion in the SiC whisker reinforced Al-Cu-Mg alloy has also been reported by Nutt and Carpenter⁶.

Another interesting feature of TEM micrographs Fig.6 is the PFZ formation in the vicinity of the matrix-whisker interface. The PFZ near the matrix-whisker interface is shown only near the large whiskers ($>0.2\mu\text{m}$). (Fig.6(b) and (c)) The most probable cause of the PFZ formation in the matrix-whisker interface is that the interface acts as a vacancy sink during cooling from the solution treated temperature. But another reason for the PFZ formation is also possible. Further work is needed to elucidate the origin of it.

CONCLUSION

In this work, particular attention was focussed on the precipitation characteristics of the SiC whisker reinforced aluminum alloy. An understanding of these phenomena is important in the alteration of matrix properties of Al metal-matrix composites. The following conclusions were obtained in this study.

1. The retardation of peak aging time in the SiC whisker reinforced Al-Cu alloy was found. However, the variation of the peak aging time as a function of reinforced SiC whisker content was not discernable. The magnitude of age hardening in SiC whisker reinforced materials was much smaller than that in the unreinforced material.
2. DSC measurements and TEM micrographs for the whisker reinforced and unreinforced materials revealed that the suppression of θ'' formation by the introduction of SiC whisker reinforcement played an important role in those phenomena.
3. The suppression of θ'' precipitation in the whisker reinforced Al-Cu alloys was considered the same phenomenon reported in the prestrained Al-Cu alloys, which might be done by a high density of dislocation in the matrix.
4. The ageing sequence of the 2024 Al alloy was altered by the introduction of the SiC whisker reinforcements. Compared with the result of DSC measurements for Al-4wt%Cu, we could conclude that the precipitation of θ'' and θ' was the reason for that phenomenon.
5. TEM micrographs for the SiC whisker reinforced 2024 Al alloy showed the PFZ formation near the matrix-whisker interface. The most probable reason for the PFZ formation was considered to be the absence of excess vacancy near the matrix-whisker interface.

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